

**THE USAGE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL AND IDIOMATIC UNITS IN THE NOVEL
"BETWEEN THE TWO DOORS" BY UTKIR KHOSHIMOV**

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Abstract:

In this article, several idioms and phraseological units of Uzbek language are given. Catching and using these idioms or phrases can be challenging for foreigners, though there are some similarities and differences with any language. However, they are highly common, so, they are being translated into several foreign languages as well as English. Therefore, the meanings in two languages can be compared by many researchers and linguists. In this work, authors compared in both languages.

Key words: meaning, idiom, describe, somebody, negative, positive, people.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/vjpy8w68>

In linguistics, idioms are utterances having meanings that cannot be inferred from the individual words in them, whereas phrases are collections of words that represent a single idea. Idioms are distinctive linguistic constructions because they frequently have cultural or contextual value. For example,

Phrases are:

- By the way: - Incidentally or as an aside.
- Piece of cake: - Something very easy to do.

Idioms are:

- Kick the bucket: - To die.
- Break a leg: - A way to wish someone good luck.

The idioms have a layer of figurative language because the literal meanings of the constituent words don't always express the intended meaning.

Utkir Khoshimov who was one of the great writers of Uzbek literature had a great knowledge using of phrases and idioms and in this work, he could use more than thirty types of units. However, no one could do any research in English about the usage of idioms of this novel until now. He was aware of the challenges of the period between two World Wars that is why he tried to express much more truly events with the help of these idioms than any writers of that period. Not only, could he describe the love story of two lovers, but he emphasized also the poor condition of Central Asian people as well as living in slums of outskirts and countryside people.

The idioms and phrases are various, here these idioms are divided into two groups according to their positive and negative meaning.

First group we consist of negative meaning idioms:

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„Qovurg’asi sanalib qolgan” it means that to lose weight and to be very thin. We use this word to describe people or animal who have become emaciated due to disease.

„Yoqasidan olmoq”. This phrase means to fight against someone. We use this phrase when we are in argument with someone and he blame us for problems we did not cause.

„Ko’z-ko’z qilmoq” means that bragging about something we have. Especially, if girls get new clothes and jewelry, they would like to brag to others.

„Itning keyingi oyog’i bo’lib yurmoq” means that always arriving late everywhere invited. We can use this idiom to describe a person who is always to be belated.

„Etni tirnoqdan ajratmoq” means to separate a person from his loved one. This idiom usually use to people divide from their relatives and siblings.

„Sichqonning ini ming tanga bo’ldi” means to be unable to find the place to escape. For example: they escaped from prison, but then they didn’t know where to go.

„To’nini teskari kiymoq”. It is usually used in the text in the sense of getting angry, offended, and changing one’s mind in accordance with different speech styles.

„O’zini yo’qotib qo’ymoq”. It is used to express a suddenly, unexpected situation in the sense of being very scared, surprised, shocked.

„Sirkasi suv ko’tarmaydigan” is phrase used for people with a sensitive behavior, and it is mainly used to express a negative attitude.

Let's take a look at some positive phrases:

„Oh desa o’pkasidan oy ko’rinib turgan” it means to compliment someone. For example: when somebody achieve success and his parents proud of him and people use this idiom to him.

„Yulduzi yulduziga to’g’ri kelmoq” means that people love each other and their characters and interests are matching. For instance, the person who you always get on with somebody but you have never been monotonous.

„Og’zining tanobi qochmoq”. Being overjoyed, unable to control yourself due to happiness.

„Kayfi chog’ bo’lmoq” means to be happy, to be joyful, to rejoice beyond measure.

In conclusion, although these idioms and phrases are not used in formal style, they are the crucial part of our speech and colloquial words and without using them we can not attract our listener or reader quickly.

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